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ОБЛАСТИ НАУКИ, ТЕХНИКИ, КУЛЬТУРЫ И ПРОСВЕЩЕНИЯ.**

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FROM THE INFORMATION SOCIETY TO THE DIGITAL SOCIETY: A COMPRATIVIST ANALYSIS

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Abstract. Research is being conducted in the world on the information society and its specificities in the following priority areas: identifying aspects such as information transformation, information culture, digital society, digital science, network society, knowledge society, global information society, informatization of education, and information construction.

In this article, a scientific-theoretical analysis is made by revealing the philosophical nature of the information and digitized society and its specific features.

Key words: society, information, knowledge, information society, digitization, digitized society.

The beginning of the 21st century is characterized by the formation of an information society in the world, the decisive factors of which are information and knowledge. The evolution of the development of this society is expressed in the transformation from a knowledge society to a network society, and from there to a digital society. In particular, in 2006, the UN General Assembly declared May 17 as World Information Society Day. [1] The declaration of the International Day of Information, the adoption of the UNESCO International Program «Information for All» in 2001 [2], the World Summit on the Information Society [3] and the adoption of the «Charter for the Global

Information Society» at the G8 meeting on July 22, 2000, [4] also put the study of information, the information society, and the digital society on the agenda today.

Philosophical-methodological analysis of the importance of information, information and knowledge, information philosophy, communicative society, cognitive society, virtuality, digitized society, systematization of various views on it is an urgent issue in world philosophical studies. Therefore, in today's fast-changing world, the need to research the nature of the information society, its specific features, and the theoretical directions related to the digital society is increasing in order for a person to understand and know the world based on complex thinking.

Social, economic, legal, and technological conditions for the formation of an information society based on democratic principles are being created in our country. In this regard, the importance of information in the process of informatization and digitization, the formation of an information society and the clarification of its specific features are becoming an urgent issue, based on the need to implement the «Digital Uzbekistan-2030»[5] program.

Foreign scientific research has studied some problems related to the information society (D. Bell, J. Galbraith, P. Drucker, M. Castells, W. Rostow, A. Toffler, F. Webster, B. Gotthard). The main attention of these scientists and philosophers was focused on studying the idea of a global information society, revealing contradictory aspects of social development of varying complexity.

In our country, there are scientific studies on philosophical, economic, computer science and technical, legal, political, sociological issues of information and the information society. In particular, it is worth highlighting the doctoral and candidate scientific works of Sh. S. Koshakov, M.N. Abdullaeva, E.M. Izzetova, N.A. Shermukhamedova, O.U. Abduazimov, O.V. Lantseva, M.A. Usmonova, O.M. Kostrina, M. Yokubova, G.O. Jalalova, H.I. Rajabov [6]. These scientific research works studied some socio-philosophical issues of information, the information society and the informatization process.

We explain by analyzing the process of informatization and digitization (information creation, processing, storage, exchange and transmission technologies) that is an important stage in the formation of an information society.

It should be noted that by the end of the 20th century, «The European way of building an information society» (1994), «Finland's road to an information society» (1995), «Germany's development towards an information society» (1996) were published by the European Union Commission. programs were developed.

On July 22, 2000, the «Charter for the Global Information Society» was adopted at the G8 meeting (Okinawa) and was recognized at the UN Millennium

Summit that year. Then, UNESCO began to study the problems of the information society theoretically. Indeed, this concept is also widely promoted in the scientific community with the concepts of «highly informational culture», «densely informational society», «information society». In short, the world community has moved towards recognizing information as superior to all goods, which determines the pace and direction of development of any society.

So what kind of society is the information society? What are its special features? What kind of society are we heading towards in the future? What is the importance of information in this society?

It should be noted that in philosophical and sociological research, the concept of «information society» is interpreted as a new society, that is, the transition of social development to a modern post-industrial society, in which the implementation of activities is dependent on the transmission and storage of information.

It is known that human society is moving from industrial society to post-industrial society in its development. If the main source of development of the industrial society is energy resources, energy production and its distribution, then in the information society, knowledge and information are the main source of the development of the society.

The concept of «information society» appeared in the second half of the 1960s, first introduced into science by Professor Yu. Hayashi of Tokyo University of Technology. According to him, the process of computerization in an information society allows people to use reliable information sources, and to ensure a high level of automation of information processing in production and social spheres.

At the same time, the basic definitions of the information society were also used in reports submitted to the Japanese government by the Japan Economic Planning Agency, the Institute for Determining the Fields of Computer Application, and the Industrial Structure Council. In particular, «Japan's Information Society: Themes and Approaches» (1969), «History of the Policy of Cooperation for the Informationization of Japanese Society» (1969), and «Plan of the Information Society» (1971). As shown in these reports, the development of the computer opens up access to reliable information sources for people, provides a high level of automation in production, and fundamental changes occur in production itself. As a result, its products become «more information-intensive» and significantly increase the impact of innovation, design, and marketing on prices.

Later, F.Makhlup, D.Bell, I.Masuda, E.Toffler, P. Drucker, M.Castels and others developed views on the information society. At the same time, the concepts of the information society of developed countries were adopted.

In particular, F. Makhlup used the concept of «informed society» in his work entitled «Production and dissemination of knowledge in the USA».

In the development of the concept of «information society», the work of the American sociologist D. Bell entitled «The Future of the Industrial Society: Experiments in Social Forecasting» is of particular importance. In it, the author divides the history of human society into three main stages: agrarian, industrial and post-industrial periods. The scientist tried to draw the history of the last period from the industrial period based on the descriptions of the industrial stage.

D. Bell describes industrial society as a society that produces more machines and goods. The distinctive feature of the post-industrial era, according to the scientist, is the transition from the production of goods (abandonment) to the development of the production of services in the fields of education, health care and management. At the same time, the scientist emphasizes that «every modern society lives by means of innovations (introduction of innovations) and social control over changes. Man seeks to see the future and plan for it.» Indeed, today, changes in the desire to understand the nature of innovations are becoming a decisive factor in theoretical knowledge. The movement in this direction is gaining momentum in the context of a unique combination of science, technology and economics.

One of the interesting philosophical concepts of the information society belongs to the Japanese scientist I. Masuda. According to his concept, the foundation of the new society is computer technology, and the main task of this technology is to enhance the activity of human intellectual labor. According to I. Masuda, «in an information society, human values change,» in which society is not divided into classes and becomes a conflict-free, that is, a harmonious, peaceful society, which is governed by a unified government and state apparatus. Agreeing with his opinion, it can be said that in an information society, not only the system of values changes, but also the importance of viewing production, human lifestyle, and material wealth as cultural leisure increases.

In an information society, intelligence and knowledge are produced and consumed, which leads to an increase in the share of intellectual labor. In this context, it can be said that «an information society is a society in which the majority of workers are engaged in the production, storage, processing and sale of information, especially its highest form, knowledge».

As the famous English scientist T. Stoner noted, «information can be accumulated and stored for later use, like an investment.» Agreeing with his opinion, it can be said that in the post-industrial era, national information resources have become the greatest potential source of wealth. First of all, it is necessary to use all forces to develop a new branch of the economy — the information branch. In the new society, industry will give way to the service sector in terms of overall employment indicators and its share in the national product. The service sector will mainly consist of collecting, processing and presenting the necessary information.

Another theorist of the information society, E. Toffler, offers a unique interpretation. In his book «The Third Wave», he distinguishes three waves in the history of civilization: the first wave is agrarian (until the 18th century), the second is industrial (until the 1950s), and the third is the post-industrial era (since the 1950s).

«The nearest historical frontier,» he writes, «is still as far away as the first wave of change brought about by the introduction of agriculture ten thousand years ago.» Indeed, the second wave of change was brought about by the industrial revolution. Today, we are the children of the third wave of change. The third wave is emerging as the fruit of the information revolution.

The 1980s–1990s can be considered a new stage in the development of the concepts of the information society. The concepts of this period are mainly closely related to the results of the research of Peter Drucker and Manuel Castells. P. Drucker introduced the concept of informationization in his book «Society after Capitalism». The essence of the concept is the idea of overcoming traditional capitalism. According to this concept, the main signs of the ongoing shift are the transition from an industrial economy to an economic system based on knowledge and information, the abandonment of capitalist private property, the creation of new values for modern man, and the transformation of the nation-state under the influence of globalization processes in the economy and society.

M. Castells takes the global economy and international financial markets as the starting point of his thinking, using them as the main features of the emerging new world. His fundamental research entitled «The Information Age: Economy, Society and Culture» is devoted to a deep and comprehensive analysis of the trends leading to the formation of the foundations of a new society. In it, the scientist called the society he mentioned «networked». Information is such a resource by its very nature that no barriers, barriers or borders are suitable for it, and based on this quality, the scientist calls the information age globalization. At the same time, networked structures are both a means and a result of the globalization of society.

A.I. Rakitov in his works envisages the transition to an information society in which the production and use of services, knowledge will become the most important products of social activity. It should be noted that the role of knowledge in society is increasingly increasing. According to the author, «the volume and quality of accumulated and processed information, as well as the possibilities of its efficient transmission and processing, can serve as the main criteria of an information society.»

N. Moiseev, analyzing such complex changes in society, comes to the following conclusion: «The decision-making of an information society will have a bifurcational nature. That is, even if the qualitative change in the foundations of development, the social nature of relations in society rejects any social

engineering, we cannot ignore the expected danger. Like any revolutionary process, the transition to an information society can lead to unexpected consequences. The problem is not in planning its development, but in preventing negative consequences (this is how this direction of development differs from a planned, controlled direction). The likelihood of events taking a dangerous turn is high. To do this, it is enough to imagine the monopolization of information systems on our planet and their subordination to the vested interests of certain groups of people. That is why the formation of an information society is a collective problem of all humanity.

In an information society, intelligence and knowledge are produced and consumed, which leads to an increase in the share of intellectual labor. In this context, it can be said that «an information society is a society in which the majority of workers are engaged in the production, storage, processing and sale of information, especially its highest form, knowledge» [7].

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of the nation-state under the influence of globalization processes in the economy and society [10].

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N. Moiseev, analyzing such complex changes in society, comes to the following conclusion: «The decision-making process of an information society will have a bifurcated nature. That is, even if the qualitative change in the foundations of development, the social nature of relations in society rejects any social engineering, we cannot ignore the expected danger. Like any revolutionary process, the transition to an information society can lead to unexpected consequences. The problem is not in planning its development, but in preventing negative consequences (this is what distinguishes this direction of development from a planned, controlled direction). The likelihood of events taking a dangerous turn is high. To do this, it is enough to imagine the monopolization of information systems on our planet and their subordination to the vested interests of certain groups of people. That is why the formation of an information society is a collective problem of all humanity. It is also a permanent integral part of the UN's problems».

The formation of an information society is leading to serious changes in all spheres of the life of the state and society. Currently, information is becoming the most important source of human and social well-being, and the information technology industry is the largest sector in the economy of developed countries. As the German researcher L. Nefedov wrote: «Today, one third of the funds spent on research and development are directed to information technologies [13].»

Since the first half of the 1990s, American and European scholars have focused their attention not on the role and importance of information in various

spheres of life, but on the value of knowledge itself. This, in turn, has given rise to new terms to describe a highly developed industrial society.

In July 1994, the European Community (EC) adopted the Action Plan «Europe's Path to an Information Society». It outlined four main areas of the European Community's activities: creating a regulatory and legal framework; developing information and telecommunications networks, classifying basic services, and standardizing equipment; studying the various social and cultural aspects of the information society; and promoting the concepts of the information society among the population and gaining public support.

Indeed, this action plan was called the «Bangeman Initiative.» Bangeman was one of the leaders of the EPR, and he led an expert group that prepared recommendations on urgent measures to ensure the EPR's entry into the information society.

In the concepts of England and France, the problem of «networks or services» is of great importance, because according to their doctrine, the creation of networks is the most convenient way to develop the service sector. It should also be noted that the main goal of all programs is the development of «universal services». The reason for this is the problem of inequality in the information society, due to which the majority of the population may be deprived of the benefits of society.

The concepts of the development of an information society developed by Asian countries are based on their national values and, in most cases, contrary to the ideas of Western scholars, put forward their own views on industrial and social development. At the heart of these concepts is «an attempt to find a connection between Confucian teachings and ongoing social changes [14].»

The philosophical tenets of «living in harmony, prospering together» are, according to Asian scholars, the key to success. Today, Japan is focused on developing its own new knowledge, technologies and products, and the focus is on innovative ideas, perspectives, and uniqueness. As is known, the population in this country is gradually aging due to the decrease in the birth rate. Despite the decrease in the working population, the negative impact of this situation on the economy can be somewhat reduced through new information technologies.

The «Asian Tigers» (newly industrialized countries) are countries that have been engaged in traditional (national) agriculture, whose economy, primarily industry, has developed very rapidly over the past 25 years, and which currently occupy a significant position in international trade. for example, include China, India, Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia, [15] Thailand.

Therefore, the concept of economic cooperation in the information development of the «Asian Tigers (South Korea, Taiwan, Singapore and Hong Kong) » is based on the state's intervention in the spending of large amounts of private capital, its targeting of specific goals, and its active participation

in the creation of material, social and information infrastructure. Among the «Tigers» is the «intellectual island» — Singapore, which has developed a strategic plan, deserves special attention. It is the noble intention of the state to become one of the first countries in the world with a developed national information infrastructure, ensuring the interconnection of computers in every home, school or workplace.

India's concept can be called the middle way concept. Because state-owned enterprises are not transferred to the private sector, but competition is widely open in the domestic services market, and foreign investment of up to 49 percent is allowed in this regard (more than 200 million families in the country have middle incomes, so the prospects for the domestic market are bright). India's main wealth and investment on the path to building a global information society are people, human resources. Today, India ranks third in the world in terms of scientific and technical potential (after the USA and Russia).

Conclusion

In the information society, human activity, knowledge is the main resource, human capital, philosophical research of information and communication problems in complex systems is important in studying the problems of our youth in the cognitive process;

The 21st century is an information society, that is, an age of information, high technologies and modern knowledge, a century of new prospects opening up before us. Because today, the penetration of information, communication and computer technologies into all aspects of our lives and their rapid development have brought great changes to our society. The basis of these changes is informatization, telecommunications and computer technologies.

As a result of the development of an information society, a large part of the population is engaged in receiving, storing, processing and using information. This depends on the timely availability of information and the ability to use it, and modern specialists in all fields require the ability to use (know) information generation (development, reproduction) and communication means such as computers and telecommunications in order to move freely in information flows. This indicates that today all countries in the world are moving towards an information society based on information and knowledge, and ensuring the rapid and high-quality circulation of information is currently becoming the main criterion for the development and prosperity of the country.

It should be emphasized that today [16] the slogan «Whoever controls the information controls the world» is increasingly becoming a social reality. The term «information age» is often used in our lives. However, as information

becomes more abundant, human spirituality is becoming poorer. Information should be the basis for acquiring knowledge and strengthen knowledge.

We do not see today's youth, who have access to unlimited information, becoming scholars or wise people. That is why sources [17] emphasize that «Information is scattered, it is not knowledge.»

It should be emphasized that in the process of informatization, it is advisable to pay attention to improving the interrelationship between culture and information in human life. Today, it is important to study and research the negative and positive effects of virtual reality, technology, modern media, in particular, the formation of computer etiquette, computer literacy and computer culture. In this situation, it is necessary to pay attention to the issues of consciousness, thinking, rational and emotional maturity, self-control, taking into account the connection of young people with reality, the virtual world. At the same time, it is necessary to provide new material and spiritual benefits to meet the vital needs of young people, that is, «the systematic improvement of the intellectual potential of the individual is one of the urgent tasks of the new stage of development [18].»

Human life takes place in an environment with its own laws inherent in human society. The issue of personal security in the information environment should be determined by the needs of the individual in modern society, in accordance with the needs of society and the state system, which arise due to the changes in civilizations and conditions that objectively arise in modern society, in order to protect and value himself, and to achieve his goals.

In an era when humanity is increasingly moving towards an information society, young people are living under various ideological threats that can negatively affect spirituality. As is known, the 21st century is characterized by the formation of an information society, in which information and knowledge are the decisive factors in the world. The evolution of the development of this society is expressed in its transformation from a knowledge society to a network society, and from there to a digital society. In particular, [19] the declaration of May 17 as World Information Society Day by the UN General Assembly in 2006, the World Summit on Information Society Issues [20], and the adoption of the «Global Information Society Charter» [21] also put the study of information society problems on the agenda today. Therefore, social, economic, legal, and technological conditions for the formation of an information society based on democratic principles in our country are being created. On July 22, 2000, at the G8 meeting (Okinawa), the “ Charter for the Global Information Society ” was adopted, which was recognized at the UN Millennium Summit in the same year, and UNESCO began to study the problems of the information society theoretically [22]. Indeed, this concept is also widely promoted in the scientific community with the concepts of «highly information

culture», «dense information society», and «information society». In short, the world community has moved towards recognizing information as the most important thing in any society, determining the pace and direction of its development.

So what kind of society is the information society? What are its characteristics and laws? What kind of society are we heading towards in the future? What is the importance of youth activity in this society and ensuring harmony of their needs and interests? It is natural that questions arise.

«An information society is a society whose socio-economic development is primarily associated with the production, „processing“, storage and dissemination of information to members of society [23].» Thus, an information society can be defined as a society that includes intellectual relations that harmoniously activate the processes of material and spiritual production based on the collection, creation, storage, processing, systematization, transmission and reception, consumption, exchange and distribution of information about objects, events, incidents and processes occurring in nature and society.

«The information society is a concept that implies that socio-economic development depends, first of all, on the preparation, „processing“, storage and dissemination of information to members of society [24].»

The informatization of society is currently being carried out at a rapid pace. Whereas “ the main source of development of an industrial society is energy resources, the ability to produce and distribute energy, in an information society knowledge and information are the main sources of development of society.» [25] Indeed, today a global information society based on knowledge and information is being formed.

«information society ” was first introduced into science in 1969 by Professor Yu. Hayashi of Tokyo University of Technology. In his opinion, «not material products, but information products become the shaping and developing force of society [26]. ” Later, F. Makhlop, D. Bell, I. Masuda, E. Toffler, P. Drucker, M. Castells and others developed their views on the information society. At the same time, the concepts of the information society of developed countries were adopted.

S. Mol, “ human values change in an information society.» [27] Researcher E. Toffler, however, gave a unique interpretation of this process, saying that «the nearest historical frontier,» he writes, “ is still very, very far away, like the [28] first wave of changes caused by the introduction of agriculture ten thousand years ago.» The industrial revolution opened the second wave of development. Today’s generation lives in the third wave, that is, the era of information.

Researcher M. Castells puts the economic sphere at the heart of the information society and [29] argues that «economy, society and culture» develop in harmony with each other. Russian philosopher A.A. Chernov [30] explains the concept of a global information society as «the growth of information

technologies and their penetration into the life of society.» Analyzing the information society, N. Moiseev argues: «In such a society, unprecedented changes occur, their negative and positive results are observed, it is necessary to be prepared for any situation in such a society, the formation of an information society is a matter that concerns all humanity, and the unity of all peoples and nations is required to resolve conflicts in this [31].

The issue of an information society in Uzbekistan has been analyzed in the doctoral and candidate dissertations of such scientists as A.T. Kenjaboev, M.A. Usmonova, O.V. Lantseva, O.M. Kostrina, G.G. Ghaffarova, M. Yokubova, A. Abdumalikov. M.A. Usmonova studied the essence and significance of informatization, the structure of informatization processes, and analyzed its socio-political and philosophical aspects. If we pay attention to the definition of researcher M. Yokubova, it is emphasized that science, information and information technology play a great role in the information society, and in this, the importance of preparing information, developing it, preserving it, and delivering it to humanity is emphasized in the development of society [32].

«An information society is a society in which socio-economic workers, representatives of science and culture are engaged in the formation, creation, storage, processing and sale on the international market of a complex of information, especially its highest form, world knowledge [33].»

emphasizes that the core of informatization is information and knowledge, practical help in improving the future and maturity of the young generation, and the necessity of an information society in determining the development of the state [34].

In an information society, not only production, but also the entire lifestyle and value system will change, and artificial intelligence, new knowledge and discoveries will be created compared to the industrial society, where all actions are directed towards the production and consumption of goods. In addition, «it is no secret to anyone that no matter what event happens in one corner of the world at the moment, a person will immediately find out about it in another corner of the world [35].» In this process, it is necessary to develop a single tool that would express the specific interests of people and eliminate conflicting interests.

Along with the positive aspects of informatization, there are also realities that cause human vices. It should be emphasized that the information society eliminates certain types of labor activity and creates new ones. It should be borne in mind that computers and computerization should not control the human mind, consciousness and thinking, but rather that humans should control technology. That is, in such conditions, it is appropriate for a person to receive information, subordinate it to himself and react to it. Thus, it should be noted that informatization processes are an important factor in determining the development of states and the future

of humanity, and it is necessary to note that it actively participates in the relations between the world and man. In turn, if the exchange of information had not been formed in the current period of human life, it would not have developed.

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